

Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis: A Case Series**Swatishmita Sahoo¹, Goutami Das Nayak², Ranjan Kumar Mallick³, Gouranga Charan Prusty⁴, Subhransu Kumar Hota⁵, Fakir Charan Munda⁶, Lity Mohanty⁷**¹Assistant Professor Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha, India⁶Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha, India⁷Professor and HOD, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha, India

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Abstract:

Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis (HLH) is a rare, life-threatening hyper-inflammatory condition triggered by excessive hypercytokinemia, resulting from an overstimulated yet inefficient immune response. Due to non-specific and overlapping symptoms with other diseases, diagnosis is challenging. A high level of clinical suspicion, along with clinical and laboratory data analysis is essential for accurate diagnosis. This study aims to present the comprehensive clinical and laboratory characteristics observed in three cases of HLH. Clinical history was correlated with laboratory criteria and bone marrow findings. This study also highlights the critical importance of early diagnosis and timely intervention to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis, hypercytokinemia, hyper-inflammatory.

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Introduction

The first case of hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis (HLH) was reported in 1952 by Farquhar and Claireaux, who initially named it familial hemophagocytic reticulosis [1]. It is characterized by a hyper-inflammatory, uncontrolled immune response triggered by various stimuli [2]. Although the disease primarily affects the paediatric population, adults are also frequently affected [3]. HLH can be classified into two types: genetic and acquired. The underlying defect in both forms involves the NK/T cell cytotoxic pathway, which results in the inability of these cells to eliminate activated macrophages [3]. This failure leads to the uncontrolled proliferation of activated macrophages.

Genetic HLH can be further divided into familial cases and those associated with immunodeficiency syndromes [4]. Familial HLH is classified into five subtypes, involving mutations in proteins such as Perforin 1, UNC13D, STX11, and STXB2, which are crucial for the packaging, transport, and release of cytolytic granules [4]. Immunodeficiency syndromes commonly associated with HLH include Chediak-Higashi syndrome, Griscelli syndrome, Hermansky-Pudlak syndrome, and X-linked lymphoproliferative syndrome [4].

Acquired HLH cases can result from infections, malignancies, or rheumatologic conditions. Macrophage activation syndrome (MAS), a variant of HLH, is often linked to rheumatologic diseases such as systemic-onset juvenile idiopathic arthritis (SOJIA), adult-onset Still's disease, and systemic lupus erythematosus [5,6].

Diagnostic criteria for HLH were first proposed in 1991 and later updated in 2004 [7,8]. According to the 2004 criteria, a diagnosis of HLH requires the presence of either criterion A or at least 5 out of the 8 components of criterion B.

Diagnostic criteria for HLH (2004)

A. Familial disease/known genetic defect OR

B. Clinical/laboratory criteria

1. Fever
2. Splenomegaly
3. Cytopenia (at least 2 cell lines) HGB < 9 gram/dL, PLT < 100,000/microL, ANC < 1000/microL Hypertriglyceridemia and/or hypofibrinogenemia, Fasting triglyceride > 265 mg/dL, Fibrinogen < 150 mg/L
4. Hyperferritinemia, Ferritin > 500ug/l
5. Hemophagocytosis in bone marrow, CS For

- lymphnodes
- 6. Decreased/absent NK cell activity
- 7. Soluble CD25 > 2400 U/ml

Materials and method

A case series was conducted in the Department of Pathology at SCB Medical College, Cuttack. It involved reviewing all bone marrow aspirate smears diagnosed as HLH from April 2024 to June 2024. The requisition forms were reviewed to gather all relevant clinical and laboratory details.

The findings from the bone marrow aspiration and biopsy findings were correlated with clinical and laboratory data.

Case presentation

A total of three cases were diagnosed as HLH between April 2024 to June 2024. The clinical features and laboratory findings of these patients are

summarized in Tables 1 and 2. The patient’s age group included a 2years male child and two females aged 21 years and 24 years. All patients had fever as the common clinical presentation. On peripheral smear examination, one patient had pancytopenia and the rest two had bicytopenia. The primary etiological factors included infections and autoimmune diseases, with no cases related to malignancy. .

All bone marrow aspiration smears, exhibited an increased number of histiocytes with features of hemophagocytosis (Fig. 1A-C). Bone marrow biopsy showed histiocytes with phagocytosed hemopoietic cells in the cytoplasm (Fig. 1 D,E). All patients met 5 out of the 8 clinical and laboratory diagnostic criteria for HLH (2004). After correlating clinical and laboratory criteria with bone marrow findings, HLH was suggested as the diagnosis for these cases.

Table1: Laboratory features of the patients

Age/ Gender	Cytopenia	S.TG(mg/dl)	Fibrino- gen ng/ml	S. ferritin ng/ml	LDH g/L	BMA HPG	Etiology
2years Male child	Bicytopenia	350	418	1500	800	+	Chronic liver disease
21year Female	Pancytopenia	255	257	1675.5	1175	+	SLE-lupus nephritis
24yeas Female	Bicytopenia	243	450	1675.56	1167	+	Hypothyroidim? Macrophage activation syndrome

S. TG: Serum triglycerides, LDH: Lactate dehydrogenase, BMA HPG: Bone marrow aspirate hemophagocytosis,

Table 2: Clinical presentation

Age/ Gender	Fever	Arthritis	Rash	Jaundice	Neurologic	Shock	Hepatomegaly	Splenomegaly
2 year Male child	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+
21 years Female	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
24 years Female	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 1A): Bone marrow aspirate showing histiocytes with phagocytosed debris in cytoplasm (Leishman stain, 100X)

Figure 1B): High power view of bone marrow aspirate showing histiocytes with phagocytosed erythroid series cells in cytoplasm (Leishman stain, 400X)

Figure 1C): High power view of bone marrow aspirate showing histiocytes with phagocytosed neutrophils in cytoplasm (Leishman stain, 400X)

Figure 1D): Bone marrow biopsy showing foamy histiocytes with hemophagocytosis (H&E, 100X)

Figure 1E): High power view of bone marrow biopsy showing histiocytes with phagocytosed hemopoietic cells in the cytoplasm (H&E, 400X)

Discussion

HLH is a disease of immune activation and excessive inflammation which can be often life-threatening. However, there are limited studies on this from Indian subcontinent [9-14]. In present study, the age range varied from 2 years to 24 years. The male-to-female ratio was 1:2 as comparable to Joshi et al [9,11]. Who reported a female predominance (M:F 1:4) while Reddy et al [11] reported a male predominance (M:F 4:1).

The most common presenting symptoms in this series were fever and hepatosplenomegaly. Similarly, Joshi et al. concluded that HLH should be suspected in any patient with unresolved fever, cytopenia, and hepatosplenomegaly [11]. Ramachandran et al. also identified fever and hepatosplenomegaly as the most frequent presenting symptoms in their series of 33 paediatric patients [12]. All patients in present study demonstrated hyperferritinemia, elevated LDH, and raised triglycerides, in accordance with the HLH 2004 diagnostic criteria.

HLH is difficult to diagnose due to its vague symptoms,

which often resemble several other conditions. Its involvement of multiple organs brings conditions like sepsis and MODS into consideration. Elevated ferritin and cytopenias are crucial clues, especially in paediatric cases where sepsis is a common differential diagnosis [13]. High ferritin and LDH levels, along with bone marrow findings, are essential for confirming HLH.

For familial HLH, the only definitive diagnostic test is genetic testing, the most common being perforin gene mutation [13]. However, such testing is only available in a limited number of laboratories. Recently, flow cytometry for perforin expression has been introduced as a screening tool for HLH. This method is cost-effective and more widely accessible, making it a potentially valuable diagnostic resource [14]. Establishing a standard diagnostic approach for HLH is challenging, as most patients present with severe illness and signs involving multiple organ systems, including central nervous system abnormalities, liver dysfunction, bone marrow insufficiency, and immune dysfunction. In some cases, not all diagnostic criteria for HLH are met, but a high index of suspicion is essential for early

diagnosis. Any patient with prolonged fever and cytopenias should be evaluated for HLH through a detailed medical history, thorough physical examination, and appropriate biochemical tests.

The medical history should focus on identifying potential underlying causes, such as pre-existing viral illnesses, joint pain (to rule out autoimmune diseases), and significant weight loss or other symptoms suggestive of malignancy. Physical examination should involve a careful assessment for lymphadenopathy, hepatosplenomegaly, and a comprehensive review of all organ systems. Laboratory tests should be conducted to confirm the suspected aetiology, including a complete blood count and cultures of blood, urine, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) to investigate infectious causes. Imaging studies, such as CT scans of the neck and abdomen, may be required to rule out malignancy.

Additional tests, such as ferritin, triglycerides, LDH, and fibrinogen, can help confirm the diagnosis of HLH. Bone marrow examination is also crucial and should be meticulously examined for hemophagocytosis. Cr release assays to measure NK cell activity and sCD25 levels can further support the diagnosis, though these tests are not widely available [13,14]. It is important to differentiate between genetic (familial) and secondary HLH, as the latter is treatable by addressing the underlying cause [13,14]. Management of secondary HLH may include antiviral therapy for virus-associated cases, antibiotics, anti-parasitic, or anti-fungal agents for bacterial, parasitic, and fungal infections, respectively. For genetic HLH, stem cell transplantation remains the only effective treatment option [15]. The 2004 HLH treatment protocol, established by the Histiocyte Society, recommends an 8-week induction therapy using cyclosporine, etoposide, and corticosteroids [15]. While permanent cure is only achievable through stem cell transplantation, treatment of the underlying cause is essential for acquired HLH.

In this series, all patients diagnosed with HLH were treated with corticosteroids. All patients were followed for a period of two months, during which they showed significant improvement and were ultimately discharged. The prognosis for genetic HLH is generally poor. In contrast, the prognosis for acquired HLH varies based on the underlying cause, with cases associated with malignancy having the worst outcomes [16].

Conclusion

HLH is a rare and life-threatening condition that remains underdiagnosed due to its non-specific symptoms, which mimic various other diseases. A high level of clinical suspicion is crucial for timely diagnosis and treatment. Given the limited data from the Indian subcontinent, this study aims to improve the understanding and recognition of

HLH, facilitating earlier diagnosis. Early detection is essential for effective management and improved patient outcomes.

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